

Electrochemical Migration of Bromine*

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Iodine and bromine though supposed to be non-conductors, conduct current in solution in inert solvents, migrate to the anode, and get liberated as such. The implications of this electrochemical migration particularly of bromine in three different types of cells are discussed in details. A solution of iodine or bromine when electrolysed in a W-tube behaves similarly as that of many electrolytes including dyes in giving three sharply divided zones.

The transport number (t_-) of iodine in absolute ethanol as determined by a moving boundary type method is found to be 1.04, which indicates that electrons pumped into the system through the cathode are carried by I_2 or I_3^- as I_2^- or I_3^- . The same mechanism of electron transport is also operative in case of a bromine solution; here the relatively lower transport number ($t_- \approx 0.55$) of bromine is attributed to the liberation of some amount of HBr gas at the cathode.

It has been reported earlier¹ that iodine, though supposed to be a non-conductor, conducts current in solution in alcohol, migrates to the anode and gets liberated as such. This brief note reports a similar behaviour of bromine and a rough determination of the transport number of bromine as well as iodine under such conditions.

Experimental

The electrolysis cell is a simple U-tube (Fig. 1. a) with platinum electrodes. Glacial acetic acid has been used as the solvent because most other solvents react chemically with bromine. The following experiments were performed, each being conducted a number of times often under slightly changed condition.

(i) A few drops of pure bromine was introduced at the bottom of the U-tube filled with acetic acid and 220 volts from D. C. mains was applied (current ≈ 0.6 mA). In an hour or two, bromine could be seen to have noticeably migrated and by overnight all the bromine was found to have collected near the anode. This demonstrated the electrochemical migration of bromine in solution.

(ii) The same was found to happen if a bromine solution in glacial acetic acid (M/10) fills the whole tube to start with.

(iii) Finally, the cathode side of the tube was filled with the bromine solution (M/10) and the anode side with glacial acetic acid only. After passing current (0.08 mA to 0.6 mA) for a few hours, all the bromine got transported to the anode side and acetic acid remained in the cathode side.

After thus confirming the electrochemical migration of bromine, a moving boundary type of experiment was done to determine roughly the transport number of bromine. Bromine solution of definite concentration was taken in a thin U-tube of 8 mm O. D. On sending current, a sharp boundary was at first formed near the cathode and then gradually moved towards the anode. The transport number t_- was calculated by using the standard formula

$$t_- = VCF / i t$$

where V is the volume swept by the boundary, C is the actual concentration of bromine moved, F is the Faraday, t is time in sec. and i is the effective current (actual current—blank current). The value has been found to be about fifty percent for M/20 bromine solution. The boundary is found to move about 5.2 cm in 24 hours at 0.13 mA current. Blank current for acetic acid is found to be almost negligible.

A similar experiment was done for the determination of the transport number of iodine in absolute alcohol. Iodine moved much faster than bromine under identical conditions and the transport number for iodine was found to be almost one hundred percent.

During our experiment, it was confirmed by actual titration that very little iodine disappeared during the migration. However, this was not so for bromine and about one-third of the original amount of bromine disappeared during the experiment No. (ii). This is evidently due to reaction of the active electrochemically liberated bromine with the solvent, as the 'blank' experiment shows hardly any reaction within this period.

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Fig. 1

Alcohols could not be studied due to their high reactivity towards bromine; however, pyridine and to some extent chloroform were found to show the migration behaviour of bromine.

As for gas liberation, bromine behaved somewhat differently from iodine; the latter liberated hardly any gas¹ during electrolysis, whereas bromine did not liberate any gas on either side for the first couple of hours or so of electrolysis, but on prolonged electrolysis for 24 hours, 60% of the theoretical volume of hydrogen got liberated at the cathode but no gas at the anode.

It has been reported by one of the authors² that if any electrolyte is electrolysed in a W-tube (Fig 1.b), generally two sharp boundaries are formed in the two inner-tubes dividing the solution into three zones namely acidic (anode region), neutral (middle zone) and alkaline (cathode region). Iodine in alcohol shows similar double boundary formation (brown/light brown/colourless) but of course showing no pH differential. Bromine in acetic acid also has been found to show three sharply divided zones when electrolysed in a W-tube as shown in Fig. 1.b. Evidently, the factors which determine double boundary formation are also at play even during electrolysis of solutions of such neutral solutes such as iodine and bromine.

Sengupta and Palit³ have theorised that boundary formation, particularly double boundary formation, in W-tube is due partially to density stratification and Palit² has demonstrated that no boundary ever appears on electrolysis in a vertical tube. A similar observation has been made with bromine and iodine using a

vertical tube (Fig 1.c). We have introduced bromine or solid iodine at the bottom of the tube, the remainder of the tube being carefully filled up with the solvent. On passing a current with anode at the top, the bromine or iodine molecules move upwards and ultimately a solution of more or less uniform color is produced revealing no sharp boundary as in the U-tube. A blank experiment shows that, if the set up is left for days without any current, there is hardly any diffusion. This supports the idea of Sengupta and Palit³ that the discharged ions being heavy tend to gravitate downwards and so no sharp boundary is formed in vertical tubes.

Theory: In the case of iodine in alcohol, it was postulated that the electrons pumped into the system through the cathode were carried by I_2 or I_3 as I_2^- or I_3^- . A similar mechanism is believed to be operative in the case of bromine too, and the transport number data support such an idea. However, since in the case of iodine, practically no gas is liberated during electrolysis whereas for bromine in acetic acid some gas is liberated at the cathode, it appears that with bromine there is a side reaction; a small but not negligible quantity of HBr gets formed and causes this gas evolution during electrolysis after some time.

References

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